

FORMATION OF EDUCATIONAL AND MODERN METHODS IN TEACHING ENGLISH LANGUAGE IN PRIMARY SCHOOL

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Annotation: The value of learning English is determined by the demands of the modern world. English has evolved into a widely utilized international communication language. This article contains some useful information about the evolution of educational and modern techniques to teaching English in primary schools.

Keywords: English, primary school, modern methods, formation of educational way, linguistic ability, pupils.

Creating a new speech system in the brain cortex while studying English in school is a challenging process that begins to coexist and interact with the already established system of the native tongue. As a result, when teaching English, we foreign language teachers face a range of obstacles. Unreasonably constructed textbooks that cover the same material but are overloaded with grammar that is not explained at the appropriate level, overloaded with unnecessary vocabulary for kids, the tasks are too difficult, and the texts are written in a language that is far from modern and adapted for kids, is only a minor difficulty.

Principal difficulties: The lack of compelling reasons for learning English and lessening the influence of one's native tongue. There has never been a need for such reasons because a youngster speaks his or her native language to address any communication concerns. As a result, the student sees no benefit in learning the language, claiming his inability to use it as justification.

The second issue is the psychological impediments that some children experience on a personal level, such as their lack of confidence in their ability to speak English, their shyness, and their fear of being teased or receiving unfavorable judgments as a result of making mistakes in speaking. When these difficulties occur,

it may lead to repeated failure, resulting in uninspiring evaluations and attitudes on the side of the English language teacher. The absence of structured instruction and direct interaction with native English speakers is the third challenge.

Modern technology plays a crucial role in language learning and teaching. The use of technology is beneficial in all aspects of foreign language acquisition (reading, reading, listening and speaking). To listen and understand, for example, it is obviously impossible to do so without a computer, player, or CD. One of the most fundamental aspects of language learning is listening. This necessitates the student's simultaneous attention to the speaker's pronunciation, grammatical rules, vocabulary, and meanings. Interactive games are becoming more common in schools today. A number of games are well known for helping pupils demonstrate their abilities, focus, enhance their knowledge and skills, and get stronger.

The action that stimulates and accelerates the student is the foundation of the usage of gaming technology. Psychologists believe that the psychological mechanisms of playful action are based on the individual's inherent needs to express themselves, find a solid place in life, self-manage, and reach their potential. The widely understood ideas and strategies of education should be at the heart of any game. Learning games should be subject-based. The student is more interested in this activity than in a conventional lecture and works more easily while playing games. The use of a computer in foreign language teaching aids in the resolution of several pedagogic issues such as:

- improving pronunciation;
- formulating and developing skills and abilities of reading;
- improving abilities of writing;
- enriching the lexicon of learners;
- training grammar;
- forming steady motivation of studying foreign language.

The Uzbek people understand the value of English in all aspects of life, including pursuing an international education, finding a good career, and keeping up

with the rapid speed of global growth. They prefer English because they believe it is the key to a happy and successful life. Language specialist Rod Bolitho attributes this significant interest in the language to two factors: a desire to study and work abroad, and an idealization of the United States and the United Kingdom. For these two reasons, he believes the Uzbek is most motivated to study it.

The lack of language in many original products can be highly enticing to English language learners. Students can look at historical objects like paintings, prints, pictures, music, movies, and maps. Using these items, students can access prior information and/or create background knowledge of the content being taught in the classroom. It appears to be common sense, but many teachers overlook it. To be effective, you must actually like teaching young language learners. At this age, primary young learners are still learning how to use a pencil, use a pair of scissors, or even speak their first language, so keep that in mind. Observing the quick development of students in this age group may be beneficial.

You might also search YouTube for appropriate baby songs to play in the background while the students are engaged in an activity that demands concentration. You only need to search for "Alphabet Song Primary" or "Farm Song Primary," for example. You'll find some excellent music that you can play in class.

Conclusion. Because primary learners are so young, it is understandable that they will struggle to communicate even in their first language, let alone a second. As a result, I would like to caution all teachers of young learners, particularly those working with children in elementary school, that they should not expect that their students will speak English naturally. Even if they are fluent in some very basic English forms and functions, they may be able to communicate and interact in very limited ways. Keep this in mind. If they are having difficulty speaking, be patient. Allow them to take their time, and you'll be astonished how far they can get.

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